

Extending the breadth and scale of scholarly evidence

The Academic Image Cooperative (AIC) aims to create a rich, high-quality, and extensible collection of image resources, selected by experts and described according to professional best practice. Currently focusing on art and architectural history survey courses, the AIC aspires to a collection capable of supporting more specialized teaching and scholarly research.

Encouraging innovation in resource curation, learning, and teaching

The AIC replicates in an online environment the curatorial and pedagogical functions of the traditional slide library. Leveraging the power of computer technology, it builds on these functions, providing an opportunity to develop a range of new tools that promise to support innovative professional practice.

Building a community endeavor

The AIC is a genuinely cooperative venture grounded firmly in the visual arts community. Its collection consists of copyright-cleared images contributed by both individuals and institutions. Its quality is ensured by peer review. Its usefulness reflects extensive consultation with faculty and visual resource curators. Its development beyond an initial prototype phase will also rely upon a community-based solution, which the AIC is investigating.

Academic Image Cooperative

The AIC is led by the Digital Library Federation (DLF) with support from the College Art Association (CAA). Funded to July 2000 by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and the DLF, and with contributions from Yale and Carnegie Mellon Universities, the AIC is presently

developing a prototype. The prototype is envisaged as a working system exemplifying what may be achieved in a networked environment by and for the visual arts community. It is a collection of images and a set of tools that may be implemented, configured, and extended locally to meet institutional needs. It is designed according to open source principles and in compliance with industry-wide standards and best practices. As importantly, during the prototype's development, the AIC will investigate organizational, legal, and business issues and produce a set of recommendations about how best to secure the development of what we hope may emerge as a vital community resource.

The prototype's development is a collaborative effort that draws upon the expertise of art historians, visual resource specialists, leading computer technologists, and business and legal advisors. Its presentation to interested communities in venues such as the CAA Annual Meeting and the Art Libraries Society of North American Conference affords a crucial opportunity to solicit feedback from potential users and contributors—feedback that may be incorporated into its further development.

Learn more about the
Academic Image Cooperative
by visiting our Web site at
www.academicimage.org

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Photos by Allan Kohl,
Minneapolis College of Art and Design

Front Cover: *Arcade between the Sala de los Mocarabes and the Courtyard of the Lions* (detail). The Alhambra, Granada, Spain

1. Greek, Archaic, *Dying Warrior from the Temple of Aphaia at Aegina* (detail). Glyptothek, Munich.
2. Claude Monet, *Study for Woman with a Parasol*. Musée d'Orsay, Paris.
3. Egyptian, 4th Dynasty, *King Mycerinus (Menkaure) & Queen Kha-merer-nebty II*. Museum of Fine Arts, Boston.
4. Wassily Kandinsky, *Improvisation XIV*. Musée Nationale d'Art Moderne (Centre Pompidou), Paris.